

http://plugin59.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

```

Search | <!doctype html>(Use /re/ syntax for regexp search)
2       <html lang="pt-PT">
3
4       <head>
5           <meta charset="UTF-8">
6           <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, in
7           <link rel="profile" href="http://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9
10      <meta name="google-site-verification" content="sQBJ98u1EC3V5-8
11      <meta property="article:publisher" content="https://www.faceb
12      <meta property="article:published_time" content="2019-02-02T15
13      <meta property="article:modified_time" content="2020-02-04T12:
14      <meta property="og:locale" content="pt_PT" />
15      <meta property="og:type" content="Organization" />
16      <meta property="og:title" content="marketingdigitaltools.com
17      <meta property="og:description" content=" " />
18      <meta property="og:url" content="http://plugin59.marketingdigi
19      <meta property="og:site_name" content="Marketing Digital Tools
20      <meta property="og:updated_time" content="2020-02-04T12:22:30+
21      <meta name="twitter:title" content="marketingdigitaltools.com
22      <meta name="twitter:description" content=" " />
23      <meta name="twitter:card" content="summary-large-img" />
24      <meta name="twitter:site" content="@mktdigitaltools" />
25      <meta name="twitter:creator" content="@mktdigitaltools" />
26      <meta name="description" content=" ">
27      <meta name="robots" content="index, follow" />
28      <script type="application/ld+json">{"@context": "https://schem
29      <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin59.marketingdigitalto
30      <link rel="shortlink" href="http://plugin59.marketingdigitalto
31      <title>marketingdigitaltools.com | Marketing Digital Tools <
32      <link rel="dns-prefetch" href="//s.w.org" />
33      <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
34      <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
35          <script type="text/javascript">
36              window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl": "https://\s.
37              !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("ca
38          </script>
39          <style type="text/css">
40      img.wp-smiley,
41      img.emoji {
42          display: inline !important;
43          border: none !important;
44          box-shadow: none !important;
45          height: 1em !important;
46          width: 1em !important;
47          margin: 0 .07em !important;
48          vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
49          background: none !important;
50          padding: 0 !important;
51      }
52      </style>
53      <link rel="stylesheet" id="wp-block-library-css" href="ht
54      <link rel="stylesheet" id="wc-block-style-css" href="http://g
55      <link rel="stylesheet" id="dashicons-css" href="http://plugi
56      <link rel="stylesheet" id="everest-forms-general-css" href="h
57      <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-layout-css" href="http
58      <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-smallscreen-css" href=
59      <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-general-css" href="htt
60      <style id="woocommerce-inline-inline-css" type="text/css">
61      .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
62      </style>
63      <link rel="stylesheet" id="font-awesome-css" href="http://pl
64      <link rel="stylesheet" id="zakra-style-css" href="http://plug
    
```

Organization

All (1)

Organization	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS
@type	Organization	
logo	http://plugin59.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-Marketing-Digital-Tools-com-Slogan.png	
image	http://plugin59.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-Marketing-Digital-Tools-com-Slogan.png	
name	Marketing Digital Tools	
url	http://plugin59.marketingdigitaltools.com/	
description	Agência de Marketing Digital Ecommerce	
sameAs	https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/	
address		
@type	PostalAddress	
streetAddress	Rua de Santo António de Contumil, 651	
postalCode	4350-291	
addressCountry		
@type	Country	
name	Portugal	
contactPoint		
@type	ContactPoint	
telephone	+3309 13 82 49 34	
contactType	customer support	